

Sargonic Empire

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This entry describes the religious practices and beliefs of the people living in ancient Mesopotamia during the period of Sargonic hegemony.

Date Range: 2350 BCE - 2150 BCE

Region: Sargonic Empire

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia, Syria

The area shown depicts the area controlled by the kings of the Sargonic dynasty at the height of imperial power.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Foster, B.R. 2016. *The Age of Agade: Inventing Empire in Early Mesopotamia*. New York: Routledge.
- Source 2: Sallaberger, W. and Schrakamp, I. 2015. *History and Philology. Associated Regional Chronologies for the Ancient Near East and Eastern Mediterranean vol. 3*. Belgium: Brepols.
- Source 3: Westenholz, A. 1999. *The Old Akkadian Period: History and Culture*. in: Sallaberger, W. and Westenholz, A. *Mesopotamien Akkade-Zeit und Ur III-Zeit. Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis 160/3*. Universität Freiburg Schweiz, 17-105.
- Source 1: Frayne, D. 1993. *Sargonic and Gutian Periods. The Royal Inscriptions of Mesopotamia, Early Periods vol. 2*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- Source 2: Gelb, I. 1970. *Sargonic Texts in the Ashmolean Museum, Oxford. Materials for the Assyrian Dictionary 5*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: N/A

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://cdli.ucla.edu>
- Source 1 Description: The Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (CDLI) includes transliterations and descriptive notes for over 8,000 cuneiform tablets dated to the Sargonic period.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Notes: From what can be seen, the contact between the religion of Agade and the local religions within the empire have a high degree of overlap, so there appears to be little competition. Certainly some deities are venerated above others, but not necessarily at the expense of another culture's religious beliefs/practices.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: BUT - that violence does not appear to be religiously motivated.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: BUT - again that conflict does not appear to be religiously motivated, necessarily. That being said, in royal inscriptions, the kings sometimes mention that the foreign god who is head of the city being conquered turned to their side, and let the Akkadian king win. For example, when Naram-Suen defeats the regions of upper Mesopotamia (Ebla and Armanum), he says it is with the aid of the god Dagan (who is highly venerated in the region) that he was victorious (see Frayne 1993, inscription E2.1.4.26).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: "Assigning" of religious affiliation does not appear to be done through any particular process. There is certainly worship of particular deities highlighted in certain cities and regions of Mesopotamia at this time, but no specific process by which this was achieved.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– I don't know

Notes: Temples own land and engage in trade. There are many people who work for temples in exchange for rations. It is unclear however if priests are directly paid by the political institution - i.e. the king's household. Rather, the temples are institutions that gather income in their own right.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The Sargonic kings named years after their renovations of important religious centers, such as the temple of Ishtar in Zabala and the Ekur in Enlil.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: The Akkadian king is granted kingship by the titular gods and is thus the apex figure of both political rule and religious veneration. This is especially true of Naram-Suen, whose inscription states that all the major gods of Mesopotamia elected to have him raised to divine status and his own cult center erected in the capital city.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Other than the king it is rare to see an official who has titles that are both religious and secular. As far as social status is concerned, there is insufficient evidence to suggest whether or not these officials were equivalent or not.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no legal code from this period that could answer this question. Legal documents that are extant only show court cases involving theft and assault, property sales, marriage contracts, and loans. None of them suggest that a religious code underlies the formation of law.

- ↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)
- I don't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

- No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

- Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

- Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

- Field doesn't know

Notes: There are certainly oral religious texts, mythology, etc. but they have not been preserved or it is unclear if they are of a status in society that should be considered revered and authoritative. For example, there are numerous incantations against demons that were probably used in ritual exorcism, but whether these texts should be considered as central to religious practice or as sacred, revered, or venerated, remains unclear.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

- Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

- Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

- Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Notes: Monuments and iconography were probably present in and around temples, but perhaps also in public spaces. There is too little data to map with precision all of the places where religious iconography would have been present.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– I don't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, given the idea that the deceased go to the underworld, there was a distinction of the spirit-mind as non-corporeal and therefore distinct from the body. But, there is no evidence which specifically demonstrates such a belief.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: There are no texts from this period that specify anything about the underworld, but based on texts from later periods, we presume such beliefs are also present at this time.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Archaeological evidence shows the types of goods and style of burial at this time, but there is no textual evidence to give further details. Some burials dated to this period demonstrate that the corpse was placed inside a wickerwork coffin (Foster 2016, 238). But this is only in a few instances and not typical of the period.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: Burials are usually in pits and sometimes, but rarely, constructed tombs.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Feeding to animals:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Secondary burial:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: But only in exceptional cases, it is not typical to have more than one corpse per grave.

↳ Human sacrifices present:
– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:
– Yes

Notes: But it should be stated that this is exceptional and not typical of Akkadian burials.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:
– Yes

Notes: Jewelry, clothing pins, weapons, cylinder seals, and other adornments are common. Sometimes professional items such as one instance of tools for brewing and making aromatics (Foster 2016, 237).

↳ Valuable items:
– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):
– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: cylinder seals, pots containing aromatics, metal pins, food stuffs, etc.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Food and drink are sometimes found in pots interred with the deceased.

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: There are a few deities who seem to be venerated as the most important, but that can vary by region and the text in which they are written about. It is difficult to say with certainty that any one god is above all others.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: But there is veneration of dead kings, family members, etc. It doesn't necessarily imply the presence of a spirit, but in the belief that the spirit still exists, somewhere.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Notes: I presume, given that they are the sprites of dead humans, but no evidence

demonstrates that dead spirits have such knowledge.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably, given that offerings of food and drink are buried with the dead and continue to be given in honor of the deceased. It doesn't necessarily mean we have direct evidence for a spirit being hungry, but it implies this is the case.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Demons are a part of religious thought in this period of Mesopotamian history. There are a few spells that exist to exorcise such beings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

Notes: An Old Akkadian love spell calls upon a servant of a god to help someone win the affections of another person.

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

Notes: Demons in general cause mishap, such as illness or misfortune, and are sometimes sent by gods as a punishment, but sometimes arrive of their own accord.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: This is usually the case, but the domains of some deities can overlap, especially when called upon for conflict.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: The god shamash is described as the all seeing deity, and appropriately so is typically thought of as the god of justice (Foster 2016, 136).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Especially when it comes to rendering justice, the sun god is sought out as the divine judge.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No specific text relates specifically to taboos in the Sargonic period, so it is unclear for now.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– I don't know

Notes: There is no evidence to support or deny this idea.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: But note that the gods are invoked as the supporters of a conquest of other lands and people; they aid the conqueror. In the same way they are also called upon as the savior of a people from a foreign invader.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– I don't know

↳ Incest:

– I don't know

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Love charms

Notes: A deity as the embodiment of love/lust is invoked in a love spell that requests the gods help in winning the affections of a lover (see Gelb 1970, text 8).

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: The gods are often invoked in the swearing of oaths in judicial matters (Foster 2016, 153-54).

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Gods are invoked in exorcism spells/rituals (Foster 2016, 156-57).

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Some legal documents from the Sargonic period invoke the gods in an oath when property is bought/sold. To go back on the oath would thus summon the wrath of the deity.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably so, but again the evidence to directly support this is lacking.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Judicial matters involving economic activity, such as the purchase of goods or property sometimes invoke a god during an oath, and therefore to renege on a deal, against the sworn oath would likely incite the anger of that god.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Several gods are called upon to punish those who would deface an inscription by the king (see Frayne 1993 for examples).

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Some magic spells are designed to exorcise demons. These demons are sometimes the servants of a god, so their presence in a household or affliction against a person could be understood as a form of divine punishment, but the cause is never mentioned.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– I don't know

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Royal inscriptions invoke numerous gods to protect against the defacement of

said inscription (See Frayne 1993 for examples).

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Against the defacement of inscriptions, especially the king. Also in a rare example of an Akkadian treaty - numerous gods are invoked to ensure it is maintained or else punishment may follow (Foster 2016, 172-73).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– I don't know

Notes: The threat of supernatural punishments in this lifetime is given (e.g. for the destruction of a royal inscription) but no text gives evidence that supports that such an event of this type actually occurred. Gods are called upon when the king conquers a foreign land or against a false king in rebellion - in that regard one might construe this as divine punishment in this lifetime.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the treaty between Naram-Suen and the king of Elam shows that blessings will be bestowed upon both parties, so long as the agreement is maintained (see Foster 2016, 172-73).

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Kings often say that the god has rewarded them. For example, Naram-Suen says that he was elected by the major gods of Mesopotamia to become divine himself, because of his victory against a rebellion (see Frayne 1993, E2.1.4.10).
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– I don't know

Notes: I don't know of any text calling upon the gods to grant prosperity of this kind.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: Royal inscriptions often invoke the gods for the future success of a king's descendants.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: Reproductive success and success for the descendants of a line is invoked in royal inscriptions.

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It does not appear to be the duty of the religious leaders to decide upon the morality or social

norms of society. The two are inseparably intertwined in that proper religious observance is a part of daily life and expected of humans in society, but there is no specific text from this period that specifically describes norms as prescribed from religious beliefs.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: There is not enough information available from the textual sources if this period to specifically answer this question.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Later periods of Mesopotamian history speak about certain purity restrictions, but during the Sargonic period there is no evidence to specifically say one way or another.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Presumably veneration of deities, dead spirits, ancestors, etc. was part of daily life, and as such it took up a portion of one's time on a regular basis.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Participation in large scale rituals occurred in two ways and was not required per se, but it did occur. The first is the priesthood of a cult which engaged in regular offerings, veneration, and appeasement of deities, presumably involving several temple personnel (Foster 2016, 151). The second are public holidays and feast days where a particular deity or group was celebrated (Foster 2016, 155).

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not clear if members of the priesthood had to be marked in some way. There was a social

marking of persons (e.g. slaves with specific haircuts or branding), but it is unknown if such marking was extended to cult personnel.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: Fictive kinship terminology is used on letters between elite members of society, usually to indicate social status of the participants and the shared relationship, which may have depended upon patronage between the individuals. But the use of this terminology is not religiously motivated, it is a social construct. The terminology is most common among Akkadian elite, and not the Sumerians.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: There is evidence of institutions giving out food stuffs as rations, but not necessarily due to famine.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Notes: There is not enough evidence about poverty in the Sargonic period to specifically say that there was institutionalized poverty relief. Presumably one could become an institutional dependent, where one exchanged their services for a set income in food stuffs, if the consequences of poverty grew dire. Again, there is not enough evidence to more specifically answer the question.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: Written education is conducted at administrative institutions in this period. It is possible that the temple institutions carried out such an education, but there is no evidence for it. Otherwise education was presumably done at home or in places of work through apprenticeships and the like.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Temple institutions in the Sargonic period are hubs of bureaucratic activity; they own their own land, engage in trade (both local and long distance), and have dependents to whom rations are distributed. The temples regularly employ formal bureaucracy both within the institution and between other institutions in the city.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: The temples and institutions provided grain and other food rations, usually in exchange for goods and services, but also to support visiting elites. It isn't necessarily public, but there was food storage available.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Notes: Temples owned land and they leased that land to farmers who managed the flow of water.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings are given to the temple regularly for the veneration of deities. Presumably a portion of that is kept by the temple. But there are no specific tax documents from the Akkadian period that show a temple levying taxes from the population. The temple has income and expenditures, but these are presumably part of the temples regular economic activities and not specifically from taxation.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: There is no formal police force, but there are certain officials responsible for ensuring the rule of law is carried out properly and for maintaining the order of society when specific needs are required, such as levying troops or a workforce.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: Judges during the Sargonic period tend to be the elite members of society, such as governors of a city. So in a sense they can belong to an institution, but do not need to exclusively.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Punishments meted out by a court were typically monetary in value. It is difficult to say if these were institutionalized because again the separation of society from its institutions during this period of Mesopotamian history is not possible.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

Notes: Political leaders are responsible for leveeing troops when called upon.

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a still debated topic among specialists. Some inscriptions of the Sargonic kings speak of feasting with a large army (e.g. Frayne 1993, E2.1.1.11, but it is not clear if that army is annually leveed or exists full time as a professional standing army (see Foster 2016, 166).

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: But that calendar varies by region and city. There is no standardized calendar used by all people in Mesopotamia during Akkadian rule.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No